

SELF-SUFFICIENCY OF FORMER 4PS BENEFICIARIES IN ISABELA: SHOWCASING THEIR SUCCESS STORIES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to showcase the success stories of former 4Ps beneficiaries in achieving self-sufficiency. The theory guiding this study is the structural theory of poverty. It utilized a qualitative-narrative approach to highlight how they became self-sufficient, the factors that contributed to their success, the challenges they faced, the contribution of the 4Ps program, and their ultimate success. The themes identified based on how they achieved self-sufficiency were attaining education, being hardworking and determined, identifying personal goals, and being financially literate. The factors contributing to their self-sufficiency were accessibility to the 4Ps program, finishing tertiary education, and having supportive networks. In addition, the identified challenges they encountered were financial difficulties, difficulty in managing time, and difficulty prioritizing their life goals. Furthermore, the contribution of the 4Ps program to their self-sufficiency was the provision of immediate needs and other necessities and applying budgeting knowledge and skills. These findings help improve the 4Ps program to be more effective and may guide the present 4Ps beneficiaries in managing their lives to achieve self-sufficiency.

Keywords: *Self-sufficiency of former 4Ps beneficiaries, Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino*

INTRODUCTION

The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) is a lifeline for many low-income families in the Philippines, offering cash grants and better access to healthcare, education, and nutrition. Its main goal is to help families lift themselves out of poverty and become self-sufficient, meaning they can meet their daily needs without relying on government support.

Self-sufficiency is vital for the success of the 4Ps program. When families become self-reliant, they need less government help, allowing those resources to assist other vulnerable groups. These self-sufficient individuals can better support their families, contribute to their communities, and participate in the local economy. However, many former 4Ps beneficiaries struggle to maintain self-sufficiency after leaving the program, often due to limited job opportunities and low wages. Despite these hurdles, some manage to succeed through sheer determination and resilience.

We need to understand what helps these individuals succeed and what challenges they face. Some former beneficiaries have used their cash grants to start small businesses or invest in their children's education, but there's still much to learn about their journeys after the program (De Los Reyes et al., 2022). This study aims to explore how these individuals achieve self-sufficiency, the factors that contribute to their success, the obstacles they encounter, and the impact of the 4Ps program on their lives.

Using the structural theory of poverty, which views poverty as a result of systemic issues rather than individual failings, this study looks at how education, job opportunities, and personal determination help former 4Ps beneficiaries become self-sufficient. It also examines the challenges they face, such as financial struggles and time constraints.

By telling these stories, this research hopes to provide valuable insights into the lives of former 4Ps beneficiaries and evaluate how well the program supports their journey towards self-sufficiency. The goal is to help policymakers and program designers create better support systems for disadvantaged communities, contributing to the broader effort to reduce poverty and improve social protection initiatives.

METHODOLOGY

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This research used a qualitative design and a narrative approach to showcase the lived experiences of former 4Ps beneficiaries. Ten respondents are from different Isabela Barangays, such as Panninan, San Mariano, District 3, and Santa Maria Cauayan City, Isabela. The researchers crafted semi-structured interview questions to guide a free-flowing interview that elicited the respondents' views of their lived experiences. The researchers constructed a semi-structured interview guide, determined the final list of respondents, explained the study's purpose, asked permission to interview them, used a cell phone recorder to record the interview, translated the data, and analyzed it qualitatively. Thematic analysis was used to identify common themes and patterns in the data related to the factors contributing to the 4Ps beneficiaries' success in achieving self-sufficiency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ways in Achieving Self-Sufficiency

The structural theory of poverty highlights that education, hard work, personal goals, and financial stability are key to becoming self-sufficient. Interviews revealed that education is especially important in breaking the cycle of poverty. Many participants who received 4Ps cash grants to support their schooling were able to find stable jobs and improve their financial situations. As one respondent stated that *"I persevered to graduate even though I came from a low-income family, and because of the financial assistance from the 4Ps program, I could buy what I needed for school. Ummm, higher education can significantly increase my earning potential, so I continued to study until I finished college"*. (Lidia, virtual communication, April 25, 2023).

Education is a powerful tool for fighting poverty. Those who benefit from programs like the 4Ps show that dedication to learning can pave the way to a secure and independent future. By boosting employability and earning potential, education offers a path out of poverty. Countries that prioritize education see significant progress, making it a vital part of any global strategy to reduce poverty.

The 4Ps are just one aspect of the DSWD's broader efforts to support welfare (Fernandez-Yap, 2022). According to Al-Shuaibi (2014), education enriches our minds, personal lives, and social connections. It opens doors to promising careers, raises social status, and builds self-confidence. In the U.S., education is often the key to accessing opportunities and achieving self-sufficiency (Carnevale et al., 2018).

Furthermore, even though there are barriers in escaping poverty, people who work hard and stay determined are more likely to succeed, which means they keep trying. The structural theory of poverty concedes the systemic barriers and inequalities individuals face; it also recognized the actions of individuals within these structures. The researchers found that respondents who revealed hard work and determination were more successful in improving their well-being. One respondent shared their story, stating, *"When I was eighteen (18), I started to work because this was the only thing I could do to help my mother. So I worked hard since we are no longer 4Ps and can no longer count on money for food like that"*. (Rico, personal communication, April 30, 2023). The respondent emphasizes that hard work and determination are essential for being independent and helpful to the family. It is a motivating force that encourages individuals to overcome obstacles and attain independence. The experience of the respondent illustrates how characteristics of being hardworking and determined can result in positive outcomes and enable individuals to escape the cycle of poverty. It highlights how individual action, combined with the structural opportunities available, can contribute to escaping poverty. Additionally, Millanar (2019) showed that the 4Ps considerably impacted poverty reduction each year by encouraging family heads, and children to work hard and be determined to achieve goals.

Moreover, having clear goals and focus is essential because they give people direction and purpose. When individuals know what they want to achieve, they are more motivated to take actions that lead to self-sufficiency. This aspect relates to the structural theory of poverty by recognizing that individuals with a clear vision of their desired future and goals are likelier to take actions that lead to self-sufficiency after exiting as beneficiaries. One respondent stated, *"It would be best if you were at least sure about everything, especially goals in life. I take time to reflect too. What matters is that I create space to process and think about goals. I have first to believe that this should be happening. I have goals and plans because it is easier for me to be self-sufficient"*. (Mitch, personal communication, April 29, 2023).

The respondent emphasized the importance of self-reliance. They noted that having clear goals and plans makes it easier to become self-sufficient. With a sense of direction and purpose, people can work towards independence and rely on their abilities to meet their needs. Mitch highlighted the crucial role of personal motivation, self-belief, and proactive planning in achieving self-sufficiency. This aligns with Riopel's (2019) findings that setting goals is essential for starting new behaviors, focusing attention, and maintaining progress.

Additionally, being financially literate—knowing how to manage money wisely through budgeting, saving, and avoiding debt—helps individuals take control of their financial situation. Ganesh (2022) pointed out that financial independence is key to success. Falling into a dynamic of financial dependence on someone else is often counterproductive to achieving true financial freedom. One respondent said that in order to achieve self-sufficiency, people should be financially literate, as stated that *“Being a beneficiary then, I learned to save money for the things that are needed... so when I had money, of course, I gradually applied to be good at managing the money I earned from work, my savings for a year well, I bought the things we need for our farm, and the rest of my savings I set aside for the extension of our house”*. (Aira, personal communication, April 27, 2023). The respondents don't see saving as just giving up things they want, but as a thoughtful way to make sure their spending matches their goals. They're all about aiming for independence and stability. They've really grasped the importance of being smart with money for the long haul. They're taking what they've learned from programs or their own experiences and using it to manage their finances wisely while chasing their dreams. In another piece of research conducted by Nababan and Sadalia (2012), as cited in Dwiastanti (2015), individuals need fundamental financial knowledge and skills to effectively manage financial resources and improve their quality of life.

Factors Contributed to their Self-Sufficiency

The researchers recognized that poverty is not solely an individual's responsibility but is also influenced by structural factors that shape opportunities and resources. When asked what factors contributed to their self-sufficiency, their answers came in one theme: accessibility to government programs on the 4Ps, which acknowledges the role of social policies and programs in addressing poverty as one of the respondents stated that *“Being a former 4Ps beneficiary gave me access to essential resources such as education, free check-ups and vitamins, and financial assistance, which helped me improve my quality of life and achieve self-sufficiency. Through the program, I could finish my studies and pursue a career I am passionate about.”* (Rhea, virtual communication, April 23, 2023). The 4Ps program really changed lives by giving people the support they needed to stand on their own. Those cash grants made a huge difference, helping folks cover bills and take care of themselves. It's like having someone there to catch you when you fall, giving you the chance to focus on learning or just making ends meet. That kind of help can mean everything when you're trying to break free from tough times. According to Orbeta Jr. et al. (2021), the 4Ps program generally has a desirable impact on the education and health of low-income families. Dela Torre (2016) supports the findings, asserting that the 4Ps Program serves multiple interconnected purposes and has demonstrated its impact on education. This impact can be direct through the program's educational and health grants or indirect by improving its beneficiaries' overall well-being. Several studies have shown that investments in human capital, facilitated by the 4Ps, have yielded positive outcomes in child health, nutrition, education, and maternal health (Bastagli et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the researchers found that education played a crucial role in the respondent's ability to achieve self-sufficiency. Individuals gain knowledge and skills that enhance their employability and income-earning potential by obtaining an education. One of the respondents stated that *“What can I say is that education I received as a BSED graduate helped me develop the necessary skills and knowledge to secure a stable job as a police officer. My background in education also provided me with the foundation to teach and educate people in my community on important issues such as safety, security, and crime prevention”*. (Rhea, virtual communication, April 23, 2023). It illustrates how access to education can serve as a structural factor that empowers individuals to break free from poverty by equipping them with the necessary tools for economic advancement. It correlates to the findings of Bohorquez (2021), who stated that individuals' success is influenced by societal factors such as education and environment. Thangeda et al. (2022) assert that a quality education equips individuals to comprehend and utilize information effectively in practical contexts. The President of the Republic of Kenya, Uhuru Kenyatta (2015), stated this sentiment by emphasizing that providing quality education benefits individuals to the development of society. It is widely acknowledged that graduates with high-quality skills and education from reputable institutions are more likely to possess the qualifications employers seek, enhancing their employability.

Moreover, having a strong support network is crucial for achieving self-sufficiency, as highlighted by the structural theory of poverty. For many, family and faith provide not just emotional backing, but practical and financial support too. As one respondent shared, *“For being firmly self-sufficient, the factors contributing to maintaining self-sufficiency are my family and faith in God...”* (Allen, personal communication, April 2023). This shows how important these connections are in helping people overcome obstacles and improve their financial situation. Family support, in particular, is vital—it's where we first learn about life and receive both economic and emotional support (Bohorquez, 2021).

Challenges Encountered in Achieving Self-Sufficiency

In the journey towards self-sufficiency, former 4Ps beneficiaries faced significant financial challenges, as highlighted by Mahinay et al. (2022). Limited personal economic knowledge often led to financial difficulties, impacting overall well-being. These struggles align with the structural theory of poverty, recognizing that a lack of access to financial resources perpetuates economic hardship. Many respondents shared their experiences, with one stating, *"I faced numerous challenges, especially when it comes to economic problems, it was hard for us to have enough money for our daily needs"* (John, personal communication, April 28, 2023). Financial constraints not only hinder access to education and basic needs but also impede progress towards economic independence. The stories shared underscore the importance of financial resources and support in overcoming such obstacles, highlighting the structural barriers that individuals face in breaking the cycle of poverty.

Another challenge identified was difficulty managing time. The structural theory of poverty recognized that individuals often face time constraints due to multiple responsibilities. Researchers found that respondents needed help managing their time effectively, especially when juggling work, education, and family responsibilities. In addition, this time constraint made it challenging for individuals to pursue educational opportunities or engage in activities that could enhance their employability or income. One of the respondents shared her story stating, *"I was working at a pharmacy in town as a part-timer. I did not expect difficulty managing my time, especially since I was studying. At that time, I had to come home to help my parents work in the fields, sometimes, I did not even go to my part-time job, and sometimes, I rushed to finish my homework. I was like a tramp who needed to act fast so I would not leave behind in the working class. Despite the difficulty balancing time for studies, responsibilities as a child, and a part-time job, I was one of the senior high school students collecting awards during our graduation. Maybe that is the result of my hardship and my sacrifice."* (Allen, personal communication, April 24, 2023). Moreover, it is found that those who handle their time effectively often find more success, whether it's managing work, school, or family duties. Determination and resourcefulness are key in overcoming challenges and reaching goals. This reflects the experiences of individuals from low-income backgrounds, who often take on extra tasks to support their families, showing how social and economic factors shape their path out of poverty (Denstadli et al., 2017).

Difficulty in prioritizing goals in life was identified as a challenge. The structural theory of poverty recognized that individuals often face complex decision-making due to competing needs and limited resources. In addition, this difficulty in prioritizing is often restricted by the need to address immediate concerns, such as meeting basic needs or managing financial limitations. One respondent also needed help in prioritizing goals in life. Respondent 5 stated that *"Along my journey toward self-sufficiency, I encountered a challenge that needed more explicit prioritization, and it was my personal goals, like what good job I would get and how I could simultaneously achieve all my dreams in life. And where I will get daily expenses for my basic necessities. I overcame this challenge by having a good plan for the next steps"*. (Mitch, personal communication, April 28, 2023).

The respondent opens up about her journey to self-sufficiency, admitting the struggle of balancing personal goals. This shows how setting goals and planning strategically are crucial in achieving independence. She credits her ability to overcome challenges to having a solid plan and knowing what steps to take next. This underscores the importance of organization and determination in facing obstacles and reaching goals. Her experience highlights the tough choices individuals in poverty face. As Demartini's study (2022) suggests, focusing on priorities helps people take control of their lives and find meaning in their endeavors.

Contribution of the 4Ps Program to their Self-Sufficiency

The structural theory of poverty recognizes that lack of access to essentials can keep people trapped in poverty and hinder long-term goals. The study highlights how the 4Ps Program addresses immediate needs which allows families to buy food, get medical treatment, and pay for school. Respondent 1 shared, *"The Program provided us with cash grants, which we used to purchase our basic needs, such as food, clothing, and free check-ups..."* (Rhea, virtual communication, April 23, 2023). This support acts as a structural foundation, enabling families to focus on education and employment, crucial for self-sufficiency. The cash assistance from the Program is intended for essential family needs, as shown by Vigilla et al. (2016). They found that most households prioritize school-related investments, aligning with Aranas et al.'s (2021) findings on the 4Ps' impact on education and health. This emphasizes the Program's success in reducing poverty in the Filipino community.

Moreover, another theme was identified based on the respondents' responses: promoting budgeting skills and knowledge as the contribution of the 4Ps Program. One respondent stated, "It is listed where I would spend the cash grant I receive from the Program, and it is separated on how to manage, for example, when I have fees at school, and the rest will be used for the foods like that. And this 4Ps Program helped me achieve self-sufficiency by giving knowledge and experience in budgeting money, and I truly believed that we should be wise in budgeting." (Mitch, personal communication, April 28, 2023). The 4Ps Program has taught recipients the importance of being careful with their money. It has led the respondents to be responsible when spending their benefits. As a result, the budgeting skills and knowledge gained through the 4Ps Program have played a role in their ability to become self-sufficient. Furthermore, Beneficiaries can better handle their financial situations thanks to the Program's commitment to financial literacy. The Program's attention to these structural causes encourages beneficiaries' independence. In addition, the manual offers an enhanced approach to providing financial literacy sessions to 4Ps beneficiaries, assisting them in their eventual exit or graduation from the Program towards achieving sustainable financial independence (DSWD, 2021). Some of the former 4Ps recipients claimed that the government initiative called the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino program helped them feel economically independent and self-sufficient. As a result, they can now manage their own money while adhering to the terms of the social assistance program (Orge et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

This research sheds light on how former 4Ps beneficiaries manage to become self-sufficient. It explores their strategies, the factors that help them succeed, the challenges they face, and how the 4Ps Program has supported their journey to independence. The study found that education, hard work, determination, setting personal goals, and learning financial skills are key to their success. The 4Ps Program has been crucial by providing immediate necessities and access to resources like food, healthcare, and education, creating a strong foundation for these individuals. A supportive network and completing higher education have also significantly improved their job prospects and earning potential.

However, the path to self-sufficiency is not easy. Many former beneficiaries struggle with financial difficulties, trying to meet their needs with limited funds. Balancing work-school-family responsibilities is also challenging, often requiring tough decisions.

Despite these obstacles, the 4Ps Program has played a vital role in helping beneficiaries become self-reliant. By addressing their immediate needs and teaching them budgeting and financial literacy, the program has equipped them with the tools they need for long-term independence. The success stories of former 4Ps beneficiaries show that with the right support, people can overcome systemic barriers and improve their lives for themselves and their families.

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